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IRIS

What is IRIS about?

Vision

IRIS will deliver a framework that support European CERT and CSIRT networks detecting, sharing, responding and recovering from cybersecurity threats and vulnerabilities of IoT and AI-driven ICT systems, to minimize the impact of cybersecurity and privacy risks, through a collaborative-first approach and state-of-the-art technology.

IRIS Architecture

- **Collaborative Threat Intelligence (CTI):** This module introduces **Analytics Orchestration** for supervising coordination between incident response and recovery; an **Open Threat Intelligence** interface for disseminating taxonomies of IoT and AI threats; and an intuitive **Threat Intelligence Companion** that serves as a key human-in-the-loop interface for collaborative incident response and threat intelligence sharing between CERTs/CSIRTs at both the municipal and national level.

- **Automated Threat Analytics (ATA):** This module extends existing intrusion detection tools with a novel threat detection engine for identifying specific IoT and AI attack vectors and includes digital twin honeypots for collecting attack telemetry against end-user systems reliant on these technologies.

- **Virtual Cyber Range (VCR):** This module is used for collaborative CERT/CSIRT training exercises based on real-world environment platforms, providing representative adversarial IoT & AI threat intelligence scenarios and hands-on training.

Project Facts

Duration: 36 months
(September 2021-August 2024)

EU funding: 4 918 790.00

Pilots: Barcelona/Spain,
Tallinn/Estonia, Helsinki/Finland

Project Coordinator: INOV - Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computadores, Inovação, (INOV), Portugal

Consortium

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